

STRATEGIES FOR TEACHING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE

Saparbayeva Gulnora Orunbayevna

An english teacher at the republican
specialized art boarding school

Abstract

English as a Second Language (ESL) is a rapidly growing field, and there are a variety of strategies that teachers can use to ensure that their students are successful. This article will explore the different strategies that can be employed to effectively teach English as a second language.

Keywords: foreign language, native speakers, cultural elements, strategies, timeline, English atmosphere.

Introduction

Teaching English as a second language can be daunting for anyone, even a real professional. Every teacher aspires to make a long-term difference in the lives of the students in their classes. English as a Second Language (ESL) educators have no doubts about their influence on students. Teaching English to non-native English speakers presents particular challenges:

- Due to a limited vocabulary range or nervousness, students may struggle to communicate or explain their confusion in full detail.
- Limited literacy in a native language (L1) can create an obstacle to literacy in a second language (L2).
- Cultural norms or classroom routines, such as raising your hand or brainstorming, are foreign concepts, and acclimation requires time.

You will find that your students, both children and adults, learn at different levels, and you'll need to adapt to each person's learning pace to ensure everyone benefits from your lessons. Although difficult, teaching a student a new language is extremely

rewarding. I have compiled a list of the top classroom techniques to help teachers along the way.

1. Create a Welcoming Environment

Creating a welcoming environment is essential for any teacher who wants their students to be successful. This means creating an atmosphere of acceptance and understanding while providing a space that encourages learning. This can include things like having a comfortable classroom environment, providing snacks and drinks, and having a positive attitude toward the students.

2. Use Engaging Activities

Another important aspect of teaching English as a second language is to use engaging activities that help to keep students interested and motivated. This can include things like using games and role-playing activities, allowing for collaboration between students, and using multimedia resources such as videos and audio recordings.

The usage of technology is crucial in teaching a foreign language these days.

Teaching methods are constantly evolving, and you, as a teacher, are constantly learning as well! The days of chalk and a chalkboard are long gone; in today's digital age, the use of technology is critical in an active learning process.

You can use short clips, language apps, and music in your classroom to connect with your tech-savvy students. You could also send questionnaires to their phones and get instant responses. Keep in mind that not all students will have access to technology, so these methods should be used with older students who are more likely to own a smartphone or tablet.

3. Incorporate Cultural Elements

In addition to using engaging activities, it is important to incorporate cultural elements into the lessons. Be aware of cultural differences.

This can involve teaching students about the customs and traditions of the country of origin and providing educational materials related to the culture.

If you teach English abroad, you will almost certainly encounter cultural differences in the classroom. Some students, for example, may believe that simply

showing up to class and not speaking is the norm. This is the point at which you must recognize cultural differences and gently shift your students' mindsets to accommodate your teaching techniques.

However, there are some areas where you must adhere to cultural norms. For example, in some cultures, making eye contact is considered impolite, whereas, in the Western world, it indicates that the person is paying attention to you.

The first step in overcoming these differences is to form a bond with your students in order to make them feel at ease in your presence and to establish boundaries. Doing so can help to create a more meaningful learning experience.

4. Provide Opportunities for Practice

Providing opportunities for practice is essential for helping students to become proficient in English. This can include providing homework assignments, giving tests and quizzes, and encouraging students to converse in English with their peers. Doing so can help to ensure that students are able to retain the information they have learned.

5. Make a timeline.

You should have a clear timeline for each of your classes from the start of the year until the end of the semester. This will allow you to stay organized and have a clear picture of your own teaching objectives.

You should also include checkpoints in your timeline where you can evaluate your student's progress and see if you're meeting your teaching objectives. Whether you're behind in your grammar lessons or way ahead in your listening classes, you can adjust your timeline to ensure your students' needs are met and they're progressing.

6. Offer Resources and Support

Finally, it is important to offer resources and support to students learning English as a second language. This can involve providing extra help outside of class, giving students access to online resources, and offering tutoring services. Doing so can help ensure students feel supported and have the resources they need to succeed.

Conclusion

Teaching English as a second language is a worthwhile and rewarding endeavor. Once you've mastered your skills, you'll be able to pursue an advantageous and meaningful career that will bring you joy on a daily basis.

By following these strategies, teachers can be sure that their students are receiving the best possible education in English as a second language. With the right resources and support, students can become proficient in English and gain the confidence they need to succeed in the future.

References

1. Bialystok, E. 1978. A theoretical model of second language learning. *Language Learning*. 28.69–83.[CrossRefGoogle Scholar](#)
2. Bialystok, E. 1981. The role of conscious strategies in second language proficiency. *Modern Language Journal*. 65.24–35.[Google Scholar](#)
3. Chamot, A. U. and Kupper, L.. 1989. Learning strategies in foreign language instruction. *Foreign Language Annals*. 22.13–24.[CrossRefGoogle Scholar](#)
4. Chamot, A. U., O'Malley, J. M., Kupper, L. and Impink-Hernandez, M.. 1987. A study of learning strategies in foreign language instruction: First year report. Arlington, VA: InterAmerica Research Associates.[Google Scholar](#)
5. Cohen, A. D. 1990. *Language learning: Insights for learners, teachers, and researchers*. New York: Newbury House.[Google Scholar](#)
6. O'Malley, J. M. and Chamot, A. U.. 1990. *Learning strategies in second language acquisition*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.[CrossRefGoogle Scholar](#)
7. Wenden, A. and Rubin, J. (eds.) 1987. *Learner strategies for language learning*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.[Google Scholar](#)